

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.0897 Max: 63.2439	1231 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No			In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 1205-1207, 1258	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:
DEFINITION crushed into floor in room 5				Covered by	Fills 1364-1366	Filled by
				☒ SU: 1232, 1241	☐ SU:	☐ SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☒ Color ☒ Composition ☒ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☒ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition			

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic		Geological	Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
☐ Pottery	☐ Nails	☐ Tufo (specify)	☐ Charcoal		☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive
☐ Tiles	☐ Marble	☐ Travertine	☐ Ash		
☐ Amphorae	☐ Quarried debris	☐ Other Limestone	☐ Animal bones		
☐ Dolia	☐ Slag ☐ Brick	☐ Basalt	☐ Human bones		
☐ Mosaic tile(s)	☐ Basalt slabs	☐ Clay	☐ Animal teeth		
☐ Mortar	☐ Opus signinum	☐ Sand	☐ Human teeth		
☐ Coins	☐ Painted plaster	☐ Silt	☐ Shells		
☐ Metal (specify)	☐ Burnt Adobe	☐ Pebbles (range)	☐ Other (specify)		
☐ Collapse debris	☐ Other (specify)	☐ Gravel (range)			
☐ Glass					
			Compaction		Color
			☐ Hard		☐ Black ☐ Brown
			☐ Compact		☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown
			☐ Friable		☐ Light Gray ☐ White
			☐ Loose		☐ Yellow ☐ Red
			☐ Soft		☐ Light Yellow
					☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: 1216	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1245
Is covered by: 1232, 1242	Covers:
Is cut by: 1295, 1298, 1294, 1311	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS

hot, dry conditions, excavated with pickaxe + trowel

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: northwest in Area B 2010

Shape: square with irregular edges due to truncation

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): very gentle slope to the south and to southwest

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

B12

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) *crushed tufo*

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

thickness: ca 0,05 m, tufo fragm. size up to Ø 5cm

Description:

floor made out of very orange (heated?), very compacted tufo fragments, seemingly without using any binding agent

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

floor surface in room 5, truncated by several later cutting activities, including the cutting during the construction of the walls 1186, 1187, 1226

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by

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